

READING COMPREHENSION -- REREADING

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ABSTRACT

Strong foundations in reading, writing, and speaking language are requirements for students. Sadly, some pupils are lagging behind in their literacy development. Being able to read and understand what is read is a necessary skill for being a full citizen in today's information-driven environment. Learning to read well at a young age is essential for children's growth and intellectual development as well as for them to succeed in school.

Introduction. The primary objective of reading is to develop the capacity to derive meaning from text. One of the most crucial cognitive skills that pupils develop during elementary school is reading comprehension. In schools around the nation, students are taught about fluency, vocabulary, drawing conclusions, background information, and metacognitive thinking. There is a statement that is frequently used regarding reading in schools: there is a distinction between reading to learn and reading to learn.

Every day, teachers put in a lot of effort to help pupils read the material and, more importantly, understand what they are reading (Scharlach, 2008). Multiple activities and keeping students engaged as they read are two key strategies teachers use to help pupils understand literature (Guthrie, 2002).

Literature analysis and methodology. According to Lutz et al. (2006), active

student participation is one of the key indicators of academic success. Academic advancement is hindered for students who struggle to understand what they read and who are not interested in it (Alvermann & Eakle, 2003). According to Guthrie (2002), one of the primary strategies teachers use to help children grasp text is to involve them in a variety of activities while they are reading.

The major objective of educators is to help children read accurately and with a high level of understanding (Hulme & Snowling, 2011). Another objective of educators is for students to be able to understand new material in addition to material they have already rehearsed extensively (Williams, 2005). Making the switch from learning to read to reading to learn requires teaching children effective comprehension skills that other "excellent" readers use (Block et al., 2002; McMaster et al., 2014).

The ability of the students to understand what they are reading is greatly enhanced

by teachers who maximize student involvement, provide real-life connections, and encourage student cooperation, according to Lutz et al. (2006). According to Whitehurst and Lonigan (2001), “children who start school behind in these areas are likely to stay behind”. Therefore, these links are crucial (p. 21). The significance of connecting connections to everyday life for comprehension was also covered in length by Lemov et al. (2020). “Reading is important for pupils’ success in and outside of the classroom” (Graham & Herbert, 2011, pp. 5-6).

Reading comprehension is crucial because students’ performance in school depends on their capacity to comprehend what they are reading (Hulme & Snowling, 2011). Students who fail to fully understand the text are probably less effective with their tactics and find it harder to understand texts that are more challenging (Mason, 2004).

Additionally, educators are aware that younger pupils create meaning differently than older students, which may explain why comprehension takes longer to develop (Dooley & Matthews, 2009). This connection is also made by Catts et al. (2016), who claim that while educators are aware that the capacity to read words is vital, understanding what is read is essential to a learner’s progress.

It can take years to become proficient in the art of understanding text, which needs a tremendous amount of knowledge and techniques (Catts, 2009). Being able to comprehend literature requires a great deal of reasoning, synthesis, and problem-solving, making it a very challenging ability to acquire (Catts, 2009). Additionally, students can only actively employ the material in multiple settings and at

different levels for comprehension instruction to be effective (Harvey & Goudvis, 2013).

Discussion. According to Dr. Hollis Scarborough, a psychologist and researcher, having difficulty with one reading skill might affect a student’s comprehension level because those skills are related to text comprehension (Lawrence, 2021). Scarborough explains how word recognition abilities like decoding, phonemic awareness, and sight recognition all combine with language comprehension abilities like background knowledge, vocabulary, language structures, verbal reasoning, and literacy knowledge to help students read and comprehend successfully. A student’s total education is significantly impacted by their ability to comprehend what they are reading.

Reading also explains which abilities are necessary for comprehension, how different abilities interact to affect a reader’s comprehension level, and which areas of the brain facilitate reading growth (Ordetx, 2021). Because it helps students pronounce the words they are reading, phonics is considered to be a crucial component of the Science of Reading.

According to Ordetx (2021), the development of comprehension abilities, like in the Simple View of Reading, depends on the acquisition of word identification skills like decoding and phonetic awareness along with language comprehension skills like vocabulary and verbal reasoning. Additionally, according to the Science of Reading, the learner’s comprehension process should be impacted by the strategic application of language comprehension abilities paired

with automatic application of word recognition abilities.

Students must be able to read words and apply a methodical approach to understanding the words they read (Townsend, 2021). All of the strands are used interactively by proficient readers who can accurately and quickly understand words. Students' levels of comprehension are influenced by elements like fluency, vocabulary, inference, background knowledge, and metacognitive thinking.

Fluency is the capacity to read quickly, precisely, and correctly, all of which are necessary for comprehension (Fluency, 2016). Fluency's effect on understanding can be observed in a variety of ways. Reading fluency issues can have an impact on pupils' reading comprehension since they prevent the use of cognitive resources for anything other than comprehension (Ribeiro et al., 2016). (Therrien et al., 2006).

There may be a nine-step method for improving fluency and aiding in word recognition, according to Pikulski and Chard (2005). These nine steps emphasize the significance of laying a foundation for graphophonics, expanding vocabulary, teaching high-frequency words, emphasizing spelling patterns, teaching decoding techniques, increasing reading speed, having interventions for struggling

readers, providing independent reading time, and conducting fluency assessments.

Fluency is absolutely important for that performance because it depends on and typically reflects understanding, even while it is insufficient on its own to assure high levels of reading achievement (Pikulski & Chard, 2005, p. 517). Students won't be able to deduce meaning from texts if their fluency skills are not developed, which are necessary for comprehension.

In order to be successful at understanding text, readers must master a variety of abilities, including reading fluency (Bigozzi et al., 2017). Decoding printed text is the initial step in developing reading comprehension, even though there are many abilities required to become a proficient reader with strong understanding (Catts et al., 2005).

In conclusion, each step of the reading process must be solidly in place for reading comprehension to occur. In turn, reading comprehension calls for inferring sentence meanings as well as text-modeling techniques based on common knowledge and inference-drawing skills. Therefore, effective understanding expands on the reader's past knowledge. Additionally, it has been asserted that hearing comprehension abilities are a crucial prerequisite for reading comprehension and are connected to one another developmental stages.

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